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**Relevance of Fracture Mechanics in Rolling Bearing :
Functional Property Determination and Steel Quality
Assurance**

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Abstract:	<p>Material property tests involving linear elastic fracture mechanics tests are established within the bearing industry. Plane strain fracture mechanics and threshold stress intensity measures are used as portrayals of the bearing steel functional properties and are used as a steel quality assurance measure. The perceived attraction in the use of fracture mechanics measures is their use as numerical design limits. For example, ΔK_{th} and KIC measures of defect size limits for, respectively, fatigue (stable) crack growth and overload fracture. The sensitivity of impact toughness testing is also evaluated in comparison to plane strain fracture testing.</p> <p>The paper reviews some of the pertinent bearing steel fracture mechanics literature and the relevance of fracture mechanics in steel quality assessment, powder metallurgy (PM) and VIM-VAR steelmaking, through hardening heat treatment and core toughness assessment in carburizing high temperature rolling bearings. The use of Ashby diagrams of yield strength versus calculated plastic zone size in fracture toughness is demonstrated to evaluate design limits for structurally loaded bearing rings.</p>

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8 **Relevance of Fracture Mechanics in Rolling Bearing :**
9 **Functional Property Determination and Steel Quality Assurance**

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19 **Abstract:**

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22 the bearing industry. Plane strain fracture mechanics and threshold stress intensity measures
23 are used as portrayals of the bearing steel functional properties and are used as a steel
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36 **Key Words:**

37 1C-1.5Cr, M50, M50NiL, AMS 6558, AMS 6560, T1, VIM-VAR, PM-HIP, fracture toughness K_{IC} ,
38 threshold stress intensity ΔK_{th} , Paris' law m
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41 **Introduction:**

42 Fracture mechanics was originally developed in the 1920's to explain the fracture behaviour
43 of brittle materials [ref. 1] and the use of fracture mechanics to explain high hoop stress
44 related bearing ring failures was reported in 1975 [ref. 2]. A historical review in 1980 [ref. 3]
45 explained the potential for the application of fracture mechanics in bearing design using
46 bearing steel tests reported in 1979 [ref. 4]. The only available data for bearing failure modes
47 comes from the "Status of Understanding Bearing Materials" publication [ref. 5]. It was
48 stated that the engine bearing failure modes in the 80's were dominated by surface distress
49 due to contaminant ingress and that sub-surface fatigue related bearing failures only occur if
50 inferior steel technologies are applied.
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53 Modern gas turbine engine steel bearing rings need to be designed to take into account the
54 exacting demands of:

- 55 • High temperature,
- 56 • Increased speed,
- 57 • Ring through cracking resistance,
- 58 • Increased loads and stresses in hybrid bearings,
- 59 • Standstill corrosion resistance in military applications,
60

- Reduced weight,
- Increased reliability,
- Cost restraints.

The relevant aspects of fracture toughness need to be considered and the testing of fracture mechanics properties is required to follow prescribed procedures such as the ASTM E399 and ASTM E647 standard methods for respectively K_{IC} and ΔK_{th} determinations. A so-called compact tension C(T) specimen is normally applied to achieve plane strain conditions (this loosely means that the surfaces of the specimen do not influence the measured values) but even then experience has shown that specimen size effects are observed in hardened bearing steels. ASTM E399-17 (section 5.1.1) states that the fracture toughness test results are sensitive to ligament size ($W-a$), with “ W ” being the width of the C(T) specimen and “ a ” the pre-crack depth, see figure A4.1 of ASTM E399-17. The dimensions such as “ a ”, “ B ” (thickness), “ $W-a$ ” need to be larger than the crack-tip plastic zone, which is estimated as $2.5 \times (K_Q / \sigma_y)^2$. This will ensure that the stress near the crack front approaches tri-tensile plane strain. For this reason, when comparing K_{IC} tests, the C(T) specimen dimensions ideally need to be stated when K_{IC} is part of the approval testing requirements. This is best done as an a/W ratio, which is typically equal to 0.5.

The test frame alignment and the fatigue crack pre-cracking are not easy for the fracture mechanics testing of hardened bearing steels and such tests are best performed at specialist laboratories.

Experimental Details and Results:

The reported K_{IC} and ΔK_{th} values were all performed according to the procedures given in ASTM E399 and ASTM E647 and the compositions of the test steels are given in table 1. The blunt notch toughness testing was carried out in accordance with the methodology described in reference 6 with the geometry of the “U” notch being shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: “U” Notch Impact Test Specimen Cross-section Dimensions.

In some impact toughness tests, standard V-notch testing according to ASTM E23 was used with the notch geometry shown in figure 2.

In some impact toughness tests on surface hardened variants, unnotched specimens were also used.

Figure 2: Charpy (Simple-Beam) Impact Test Specimen, Type A, with V-notch geometry.

Steel Grades:	Code or Spec.	C	Cr	Mn	Si	Cu	P	S	Mo	Ni	V	Co	W	Other:
1C-1.5Cr	C	1.07	1.50	0.34	0.26	0.15	0.005	0.016	0.03	0.08	-			Oxygen 12 ppm
	L	1.00	1.50	0.34	0.25	0.10	0.015	0.02	0.04	0.10	-			Oxygen 23 ppm
	SR	1.02	1.39	0.33	0.22	0.13	0.006	0.015	0.02	0.06	-			Oxygen 47 ppm
M50	AMS 6490	0.80	4.00	0.30	≤0.25	≤0.10	≤0.015	≤0.015	4.25	≤0.015	1.00	≤0.25	≤0.25	-
M50	PM-HIP test steel	0.82	4.26	0.25	0.60	0.094	0.014	0.005	4.10	0.16	1.09	0.29	0.76	-
M50NiL	AMS 6278	0.13	4.00	0.30	0.18	≤0.10	≤0.015	≤0.010	4.25	3.50	1.20	≤0.025	≤0.015	-
RBD	X20WCr10	0.2	3.0	0.30	≤0.35	-	≤0.20	≤0.15	-	0.70	0.425	-	10.0	-
Pyrowear 675	AMS 5930	0.07	13.00	0.75	0.40	-	≤0.015	≤0.010	2.0	2.60	0.60	5.4	-	-
18-4-1	T1 ASTM A600-92a	0.73	4.00	0.25	0.30	-	≤0.03	≤0.03	-	-	1.10	-	18.0	-
M62	AMS 6558	1.33	3.70	0.30	0.28	-	≤0.03	≤0.03	10.50	-	1.95	≤1.0	6.13	-
7-7-7-11	AMS 6560	2.3	4.2	0.30	0.60	-	≤0.03	≤0.03	7.0	-	6.5	10.5	6.5	-
ASP2023		1.28	4.1			-	≤0.03	≤0.03	5.0		3.1	-	6.4	

Table 1: Bearing Steel Compositions (wt.%)

Effect of Micro Inclusions on K_{IC} and ΔK_{th}

In 1989 [ref. 6], the results of a detailed K_{IC} and ΔK_{th} test programme were reported for three qualities of 1C-1.5Cr steel with various through hardening heat treatments. The 1C-1.5Cr steel quality at that time was characterized by the oxygen content, see table 1. If the fracture mechanics properties are compared for the three through hardening heat treatments, no significant difference can be observed in the K_{IC} (load ratio $R = 0.1$) fracture mechanics properties, see figure 3.

There is no relationship between the ΔK_{th} values and the steel micro-cleanliness for a given heat treatment, see figure 4.

Figure 3: Summary of K_{IC} Relationships with Hardened 1C-1.5Cr Steel Quality

Figure 4: Summary of ΔK_{th} ($R=0.1$) Relationships with Hardened 1C-1.5Cr Steel Quality

The lack of sensitivity of the measured K_{IC} and ΔK_{th} values to oxide micro-cleanliness implies that fracture mechanics tests have limited merit as steel quality assurance measures.

Influence of Through Hardening Heat Treatment on K_{IC} and ΔK_{th} in 1C-1.5Cr Steels:

With reference to figures 3 and 4 it can be observed that the three 1C-1.5Cr steel qualities (oxide micro-cleanliness) show no significant K_{IC} variation values. However, regarding crack initiation, an increase of ΔK_{th} value is clearly observable for the bainitic heat treatment. The bainitic hardened state of 1C-1.5Cr is showing retardation to crack growth with a value of about $7.8 \text{ MPa}\cdot\sqrt{\text{m}}$ (± 0.5) compared to stabilized martensite $5.4 \text{ MPa}\cdot\sqrt{\text{m}}$ (± 0.6) and martensite $4 \text{ MPa}\cdot\sqrt{\text{m}}$ (± 0.2). This result was confirmed in a later test programme and can be attributed to the presence of a compressive stress field as a result of the applied bainitic heat treatment and the resultant crack closure. Indeed, the structural toughness superiority of the bainite compared to the martensite of similar hardness is probably a function of the lower tensile stresses [ref. 7] or the slight compressive residual stress or the beneficial effect of the fine carbide dispersion in the lower bainitic microstructures [ref. 6].

Steelmaking Effects on Fracture Toughness PM-HIP vs VIM-VAR M50

A comprehensive powder metallurgy – hot isostatic pressing (PM-HIP) and vacuum induction melting – vacuum arc refining (VIM-VAR) M50 steel test programme was reported in 2016 as part of the SKF University Steel Technology Centre R&D activities at the University of Cambridge [ref. 8]. In this project, M50 steel produced by the standard VIM-VAR steelmaking was compared with similar steel produced by high quality PM-HIP process and both fracture mechanics K_{IC} and impact toughness testing were applied. With reference to Figure 5, it will be observed that the VIM-VAR material had a higher fracture toughness than the harder PM-HIP secondary hardened steel.

Figure 5: Transverse (L-C) and Longitudinal (C-L) Fracture Toughness of Hardened M50 Steels

It is significant that the measured fracture toughness properties did not reflect the known anisotropy of the VIM-VAR M50 microstructure [ref. 8]. This will be commented on in the next section.

Through Hardened High Speed Steel Fracture Toughness:

Through hardening high speed steels (HSS) have been used for rolling bearings in high temperature rotating applications since the early 1900's, initially using T1 (18-4-1), later M50 and nowadays with PM-HIP AMS 6558 and AMS 6560, see figure 6. The T1 steel is characterized as having a predominance of large primary carbides, due to the high tungsten content, while the AMS 6558 and AMS 6560 variants have very high hardness's and fine carbide microstructures [ref. 9]. The through hardening steels are not used in applications where tolerance to structural loading is required and the PM-HIP steel AMS 6560 has an exceptionally good rolling contact fatigue strength [ref. 9].

Figure 6: Bearing Steel Historical Developments

The fracture toughness of T1 and M50 was reported in 1979 [ref. 4] and if the reported K_{IC} and hardness values are plotted with recent PM-HIP HSS's, a reasonable correlation is observed, see figure 7.

Figure 7: Fracture Toughness - Hardness Relationship for Through Hardening HSS's

The comparative VIM-VAR M50, PM-HIP M50, AMS 6558 and AMS 6560 steel longitudinal-transverse fracture toughness properties are in addition plotted in figure 8. The C-L sample orientation (generally sampled at mid-radius) corresponds to a crack that propagates along the longitudinal direction. The L-C direction corresponds to a crack that will propagate circumferentially (this is the transverse fracture toughness value).

Figure 8: Transverse (L-C) vs. Longitudinal (C-L) Fracture Toughness of HSS's for Bearings

The range of microstructures in the VIM-VAR and the PM-HIP high speed would imply that a hardness and a microstructure model can be developed with the VIM-VAR M50 having numerous large primary carbides whereas the PM-HIP steels have numerous fine carbides. It can be observed in the literature from Leskovsek et al. [ref. 10] that carbide mean free path distances and carbide volume fraction can be related to fracture toughness. The relationship has been established for HSS M2 steel. This means that the M50 VIM-VAR microstructure with large primary carbides high mean-free path distances and relatively low volume fraction of carbide has a higher fracture toughness than for example AMS 6560 with a high volume fraction of (fine) carbide and a low carbide mean-free path. Using the empirical formula [ref. 10], the results for three different hardness's and microstructures of high speed steels are shown in the following table 2:

	E = Young Modulus (MPa)	d_p =Carbide Mean free path (μm)	Carb. Vol. fraction (f_{carb})	Austenite fraction	Hardness (HRC)	K_{IC} (experi- mental) ($\text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$)	K_{IC} (calculated) ($\text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$)
M50 VIM-VAR (AMS 6491)	203 000	13,1	0,114	0,03	63,5	18	19,9
AMS 6560	250 000	7,9	0,4	0	68	9,5	10,1
PM M62 (AMS 6558)	236 000	4,2	0,28	0	66,2	11,5	8,4

Table 2: Microstructural & hardness parameters and experimental and calculated values of ultimate fracture toughness for three different HSS's.

The results plotted in figure 9 show a reasonable fit to the model to explain the fracture toughness of such HSS. This is an interesting approach as a prediction of the K_{IC} value can be obtained according to the HSS microstructure.

Figure 9 : Experimental vs. Modelled KIC values for three different HSS's.

Carburized HSS Fracture Toughness

An early example of the application of fracture toughness in bearing steels involved the load limit modelling based on the core toughness of carburized M50 NiL. The presence of near surface compressive residual stress was seen a part of the benefits of M50 NiL [ref. 11]. By stress level superposition, the stress intensity in the fracture toughness models can be comprehended. Based on the experience with M50 NiL, a compressive stress is seen as a pre-requisite in state-of-the-art aerospace bearing steels. However, counter to this, the steel grade RBD was successfully introduced in the late 1940's and is still used today with good results despite that fact that RBD does not develop a compressive stress as a result of the carburization and secondary hardening heat treatment [ref. 12].

A publication from 1998 [ref. 13] showed the benefit of secondary hardening tempering treatments on the toughness of carburized and hardened M50NiL. The "V" notch impact toughness, expressed as K_Q in $\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ units, is reported against depth from the notch for different 2 hour tempering temperatures. Obviously, the toughness increases into the tough core with both the retained austenite and the compressive residual stress correspondingly decreasing. Note that this refers to K_Q values not true K_{IC} values. K_Q is the measured toughness value before validation of the test conditions.

The core fracture toughness of a number of carburised HSS's for bearings was reported in 2002 [ref. 14]. Fracture toughness data for M50 NiL had been published in 1985 [ref. 15], reporting a K_{IC} core toughness value of $51 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ obtained from ASTM E399 C(T) specimen testing and a K_{IC} value of $43 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ is given in the 2007 Latrobe data sheet [ref. 16] for CBS-50 NiL. As carburized M50NiL rings are well established in aeroengine mainshaft bearings to support the structural loading, these K_{IC} values could be kept as minimum target requirements.

The core toughness of Pyrowear 675 steel in the high temperature tempering condition is a key development focus for current and future hybrid aero-engine bearings. Information on the Pyrowear 675 core fracture toughness properties is presented in figure 10.

Figure 10: Fracture Toughness Information on Pyrowear 675 Core Steel.

Contrary to the through hardened high hardness test variants, fracture mechanics tests on Pyrowear 675 core material show the slight anisotropic nature of the VIM-VAR steels. Different heat treatments have been applied to the Pyrowear 675 variants: "P675 HTT" was cryogenically treated and double tempered at 496°C. The Böhler variants A and B have been cryogenically treated and tempered once at 515°C. The variation of fracture toughness (K_{IC} value) due to anisotropy is in the range of 9 to 15%.

"P675 – Bohler A" and "P675 – Bohler B" C(T) specimens were hot forged with different reduction ratios, and the slightly decreased anisotropy shown from B compared to A seems correlated to the increased reduction ratio.

These values from about 60 to 80 MPa√m for P675 in the high temperature tempered condition are acceptable for mainshaft applications but the minimum toughness needed depends on the actual structural fatigue loading in the application. The test result from "P675 - Bohler C" is only a K_Q value, which cannot be considered as a valid result due to the insufficient specimen size used for this test.

The measurement of the tolerance to structural loads in the presence of sharp crack is a key attribute of linear elastic fracture mechanics testing and, in this respect, it can be relevant to look at the Paris' law region i.e. the linear region of the $da/dN - \Delta K$ curves. The Paris' law region relates the linear stress intensity factor range to the sub-critical crack growth during fatigue crack growth, see figure 11.

Figure 11: Paris' Law Region (Region II) of Fatigue Crack Growth Curve

Paris' law is a popular fatigue crack growth model used in material science, the basic formula reads:

$$da/dN = C.\Delta K^m$$

The term "a" is the crack length, N is the number of load cycles and C and m are material constants. The term m can be obtained by regression of the stable crack growth da/dN versus ΔK region in a log – log plot for a given load ratio R ($R = F_{min}/F_{max}$); normally 0.1.

The ASTM E647-15e1 "Standard Test Method for Measurement of Fatigue Crack Growth Rates" contains a significant amount of information about specimen dimensions and test procedures but nothing is specified on the Paris' law m parameter measurement. The Pugno et al. publication "A generalized Paris' law for fatigue crack growth" [ref. 17] does not give any explicit recommendations on the topic. The "trendline" power option was used for the linear portion of the da/dN vs. ΔK log – log plots, and the exponent extracted is the value ie. the required m value.

The only published m values for crack growth in bearing steels are those from the MIT thesis on through hardening secondary hardening steels M50 and T1 (18-4-1) [ref. 18].

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3 The literature contains $da/dN - \Delta K$ plots at $R = 0.1$ for M50 and the hardened core region of
4 M50 NiL [ref. 15].
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6 For the core microstructures of aerospace carburising steel grades, only M50 NiL data is
7 available. The m values are summarized in table 3 and the plots are shown in figure 12.
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Steel & Heat Treatments:	m Values	References:
M50 Through hardened	3	MIT thesis [ref. 17]
T1 Through hardened	4	
M50 tempered 3 times 540°C	2.92	Reanalysis of Averbach et al data [ref. 14]
M50 tempered 5 times 540°C	3.24	
M50 tempered 5 times 650°C	2.93	
Core M50 NiL	2.73	
Case carburized M50 NiL	3.12	

Table 3: Summary Information on m Values for Aerospace Bearing Steels

Figure 12: Summary of Paris' Law (Stable Crack Growth) Data

The less tough through hardened or carburised case microstructures and tougher carburised core microstructures were generally similar with respect to the m values (rate of crack growth) at any given stress intensity for the tested R ratio, as shown in figure 12. The evidence is that the rate of stable crack growth is similar for all of the tested aerospace bearing steels, irrespective of the composition and microstructures. This implies that the m value is phenomenological and that the Paris' law is empirical and has no physical metallurgy basis in heat treated aerospace bearing steels.

Materials Selection Based on Fracture Mechanics in Rolling Bearing Design:

The book Michael F. Ashby, "Materials Selection in Mechanical Design" Elsevier, Third Edition 2005 explains the plastic zone size concept at the tip of a stress concentration. The plane strain fracture toughness is scaled approximately with the strength of the material (yield stress σ_y) within the plastic zone size d_y . The plastic zone size is obtained by substitution into the equation:

$$d_y = 1/\omega \times (K_{IC}/\sigma_y)^2$$

The Ashby approach has an application in selecting materials for the safe design of structurally loaded components. The diameter of the plastic zone at a crack tip is indicative of the toughness and can be used as a design guideline for damage-tolerant steel technology usage.

The relevant yield strength and fracture toughness values of the core materials are given in table 4 and plotted in figures 13 and 14. The open symbols in the figures apply to case carburized or nitrided bearing steel variants.

The optimum design would be a high yield strength combined with a high fracture toughness (which corresponds to the top right hand corner of the Ashby plot).

Steels	Approximate Heat Treatment Temperatures (°C)	K_{IC} (MPa√m)	Yield Strength σ_y (MPa)	Calculated Plastic Zone Size (μm)	Source:	
18-4-1	1250 austenitize – temper 540	20	2351	23	Jose Antonio Rescalvo Santiago "Fracture and Fatigue Crack Growth in 52100, M-50 and 18-4-1 Bearing Steels", MS Thesis, Massachusetts Institute of Technology 1976	
	Temper 555	21	2299	27		
	Temper 560	21	2260	28		
	Temper 580	22	2156	33		
	Temper 595	22	2000	39		
M50	1095°C austenitize – temper 510	17.5	2048	23		
	Temper 530	17.5	2190	20		
	Temper 538	17.5	2309	18		
	Temper 553	18.5	2309	20		
	Temper 565	20	2286	24		
52100	815 austenitize –temper 135	18.1	1550	43		
	Temper 150	19.5	1600	47		
	Temper 170	19.5	1650	44		
	Temper 195	19.7	1850	36		
	Temper 230	17.5	2100	22		
	845 austenitize – temper 135	18	1400	52		
	Temper 150	18	1450	49		
	Temper 170	18	1550	43		
	Temper 195	18	1750	34		
	Temper 230	17.1	2150	20		
	870 austenitize – temper 135	16.4	1250	54		
	Temper 150	17.5	1300	58		
	Temper 170	17.5	1350	53		
Temper 195	17.5	1500	43			
Temper 230	16	2250	16			
M50	1095 austenitize - 540 temper	23	2275	33		Averbach et al Metallurgical Transactions A, Volume 16A, July 1985, p 1253
M50 NiL	1095 austenitize - 540 temper	51	1210	565		A. Iqbal and J.E. King, The Role of Primary Carbide in Fatigue Crack Propagation in Aeroengine Steels", Int. J. Fatigue July, 1990, p 234
Volvic	1150 austenitize – 550 temper	29	1410	135		Böhler internal information
RBD	1110 austenitize – 560 temper	30	1200	199		
M50	1100 austenitize – 540 temper	22	2350	28		SKF
18-4-1	1240 austenitize – 560-540 temper	29	2048	64		
	1260 austenitize – 560-540 temper	27	2020	57		
Pyrowear 675	1038 austenitize - 515 temper	63.8	995	1309	Averbach et al Metallurgical Transactions A, Volume 16A, July 1985, p 1267	
	1038 austenitize – 515 temper	66.8	1010	1392		
52100	Bainite	22	2200	32	Latrobe data sheet & STP 1419 p366	
X-2M	1065 austenitize – 525 temper	51	1240	538	CarTech extended data sheet, 2009	
M50 NiL	1095 austenitize – 540 temper	52	1210	588		
CBS-1000M	1095 austenitize – 540 temper	49	1270	474	SKF UTC tests and conversion of HRC vs compression yield strength test data	
CSS-42L	1093 austenitize – 496 temper	109	1336	2119		
Pyrowear 675	1038 austenitize – 510 temper	86	1062	2087	ASTM STP 1327 pp 391-405	
AMS 6560	~1150 austenitize – 560 temper	9.6	3800	2		
AMS 6558		11.6	3200	4		
32CDV13	900-950 austenitize – 625-650 temper	154	1054	6730	ASTM STP 1419 pp 362-374	
Cronidur 30	1030 austenitize – 160-180 temper Or 220-300	16	1850	24		

Table 4: Bearing Steel Property Information

Figure 13: Bearing Steel Yield Strength versus K_{IC}

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Figure 14: Bearing Steel Yield Strength versus Log Calculated Plastic Zone Size

Notched Impact Toughness Properties:

It is understood that impact testing, in the presence of a well-controlled notch, provides meaningful information in a short period of time at considerably lower cost than plane strain fracture mechanics testing. As an example of the benefit of impact testing, some anisotropy of the PM-HIP HSS's can be recognized from the blunt U-notch impact toughness data shown in figure 15.

Figure 15: Transverse (L-C) vs. Longitudinal (C-L) Blunt U-Notch Impact Toughness Properties at room temperature for HSS's [ref. 8]

Figure 15 shows that the blunt notch impact test results reflect the anisotropy seen in the microstructure of VIM-VAR M50 and the isotropy seen in the microstructures of the three PM steel variants [ref. 7 & 8]. It is clear from figure 8 that the K_{IC} fracture toughness test is insensitive to the microstructure anisotropy in this hardened high speed steel.

The classical V-notch used in Charpy impact testing in ASTM E23 is generally attractive, giving a reproducible starting point of the fracture due to its high level stress raising effect. Indeed the V-notch sample is increasing the stress in the plastic zone by a factor of 2.52 located at 0.56 mm from the tip of the notch. However, for such high speed tool steels, it is not giving sufficient discrimination power between variants and the tests on through hardened HSS comparing V-notch with U-notch impact testing is shown in figure 16.

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5 **Figure 16:** Impact Toughness of PM Grades (ASP2055 and AMS 6560) vs. M50 at Room
6 Temperature: U and V Notches (Plotted Error bars are Standard Deviations).
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10 It should be noted that it is advised in the ASTM standard to use an un-notched geometry for
11 PM steels. However, the opening of the crack path is not guided and the results are generally
12 less reproducible. Under certain circumstances, such as shallow surface hardening
13 treatments, unnotched impact testing may be the only practical test method.
14

15 A U-notch allows sensitive discrimination of the toughness for hardened steels whilst retaining
16 a good reproducibility (expected to be higher than in un-notched configuration). The room
17 temperature impact U-notch toughness-hardness relationship is again plotted at room
18 temperature (for VIM-VAR M50, ASP2023, ASP2055, PM M62 and AMS 6560).
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23 **Figure 17:** U-Notch Impact Toughness vs. Hardness (at RT) for Through Hardened HSS's
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28 Ideally the effect of the application temperature should be considered and this is best
29 evaluated by the use of impact testing. Figure 18 shows that for M50, the expected increase
30 in toughness is seen from room temperature to the highest tested temperature of 150°C ;
31 while for ASP 2055 and AMS 6560 PM-HIPed variants, the increase in toughness with
32 increasing temperature is more modest. This may be due to the fact that there is a lower
33 decrease in the elastic limit with temperature for both PM-HIPed variants as compared to
34 VIM-VAR M50. No decrease in toughness between room temperature and -200°C is observed
35 for ASP 2055 and AMS 6560. For M50, there is clearly a lower toughness at -200°C but the
36 rate of decrease in toughness with sub-zero temperatures seems to be lower than the rate of
37 increase in toughness for temperatures above ambient temperature.
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44 **Figure 18:** U-Notch Impact Toughness (Resiliency) in Transverse or Radial fracture as a
45 Function of Temperature for Through Hardened HSS's
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51 The yield strength dependency of temperature could be the main reason to explain the two
52 observed toughness behaviours of M50 versus the PM ASP variants. The yield strength as a
53 function of temperature for M50 probably decreases faster than for ASP2055 and AMS 6560.
54 The assumption is that this is due to the lower content of thermally stable carbides in M50.
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57 An advantage of the impact toughness test is its ability to illustrate the effect of surface
58 thermochemical treatments on the toughness properties. Unnotched samples results are
59 shown in Figure 19. Impact tests were performed on carburized and carburized plus nitrided
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3 specimens of M50 NiL. Note that the white layer was removed after the nitriding treatment.
4 The fracture initiation happens from the nitriding diffusion treated surface. Figure 19 indicates
5 that nitriding applied on the case carburized surface significantly increases the surface
6 hardness but also reduces the fracture energy.
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10 **Figure 19:** Impact Toughness (un-notched sample) at room temperature for M50 NiL steel
11 with different surface diffusion layers.
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15 The inference from the impact testing is that nitriding can be applied to bearing races but
16 should preferably be avoided on non-working contact regions subjected to structural loads.
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20 Discussion:

21 The available fracture mechanics information shows that an increase in hardness results in a
22 correspondingly lower plane strain fracture toughness for **through hardened** bearing steels,
23 irrespective of the oxide micro-cleanliness.
24

25 For through hardened bearing steels, the degree of anisotropy - as is present in VIM-VAR
26 steels - can be evaluated more easily and more cost effectively by using blunt U-notch impact
27 toughness testing rather than plane strain fracture mechanics testing.
28

29 The comparison of HSS toughness's has been done with room temperature data. Aeroengine
30 bearings are used at higher temperatures (100-300°C for example). The temperature effect
31 on impact toughness has been assessed on through hardened steels (PM-HIPed and VIM-VAR
32 steelmakings) in the temperature range -196 to 150°C. An extension of the investigated
33 temperature to higher values will be valuable to determine the toughness of through
34 hardened steels at the application temperatures.
35

36 Martensitically through hardened bearing steels have similar threshold stress intensity values
37 for a given hardness and the Paris' law m values similarly show no significant trend for the
38 analysed steels, case or core hardened or through hardened. However, bainitic through
39 hardening of 1C-1.5Cr steel measurably increases the threshold stress intensity values, which
40 corresponds with the known improved tolerance to structural loads as compared to
41 martensitic through hardened bearing steel of similar hardness.
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44 The **core properties** of carburized highly alloyed, temperature resistant secondary
45 hardening bearing steels can be usefully characterized by applying ASTM E399 K_{IC} testing.
46 Because of the higher toughness, larger C(T) specimens need to be applied as compared with
47 (less tough) through hardening steels. Because of the slight observed anisotropy of K_{IC} in the
48 core microstructures, the K_{IC} tests need to be performed in the longitudinal and transverse
49 directions and the acceptance limits or design limits need to take into account the VIM-VAR
50 steel anisotropy.
51

52 **For structurally loaded bearings** (eg. with flanged ring or geared-ring), the philosophy of
53 "damage-tolerant design" is used to ensure that the component integrity is guaranteed for
54 the expected service life. In practice, this means that a minimum toughness is needed to
55 account for variations in the operating conditions.
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Conclusions:

Application of plane strain fracture mechanics:

- For bearing steels, the plane strain fracture toughness decreases with increasing hardness.
- For through hardened High Speed Steels (HSS), the plane strain fracture toughness is insensitive to oxide micro-cleanliness, so the method is not suitable as a steel quality assurance measurement.
- The plane strain fracture toughness is insensitive to the anisotropy of through hardened microstructures.
- Bainite through hardening slightly increases the fracture toughness and significantly increases the threshold stress intensity value compared to martensite through hardening for the same hardness.
- The empirical model from Leskovsek (ref. 10) seems to explain the fracture toughness of HSS by taking into account the hardness and the microstructural parameters such as carbide content, carbide mean-free path distance, retained austenite fraction and elasticity. This model should be further investigated and validated.
- Plane strain fracture toughness testing can reveal anisotropy in the hardened core microstructures of carburising steels. In other words, the core property characterization in carburized bearing rings is an example of the purposeful use of plane strain fracture mechanics.
- The Ashby diagrams which plot yield strength versus calculated plastic zone size (based on K_{IC} value), are an expedient way to evaluate design limits in structurally loaded bearing components.

Fatigue Crack growth rate:

- The slope "m" of the Paris' Law for crack growth rate does not vary significantly for through hardened or carburised steels. The Paris' law is empirical and has no physical metallurgy basis in heat treated aerospace bearing steels.

Application of impact toughness testing

- Impact testing easily discriminates anisotropy for through hardened steels. Blunt U-notch impact energy is sensitive to the strength and microstructure of through hardened high carbon steels.
- U-notch impact toughness testing has more discrimination power than V-notch impact toughness testing.
- It is worth noting that this test method is simpler and more cost effective than K_{IC} testing.
- Further work could be done to study the effect of high and low temperature on the impact and fracture toughness.
- Fracture mechanics and impact toughness testing will be increasingly important with the development of Powder Metallurgy steels with higher strengths and hardness's.

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Notch Geometry

$$a = 0,15 \pm 0,015 \text{ mm}$$

$$b = 0,17 \pm 0,005 \text{ mm}$$

"U" Notch Impact Test Specimen Cross-section Dimensions

32x27mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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Charpy (Simple-Beam) Impact Test Specimen, Type A, with V-notch geometry
35x17mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Summary of KIC Relationships with Hardened 1C-1.5Cr Steel Quality

59x36mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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Summary of ΔK_{th} (R=0.1) Relationships with Hardened 1C-1.5Cr Steel Quality
59x36mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Transverse (L-C) and Longitudinal (C-L) Fracture Toughness of Hardened M50 Steels

37x21mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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Bearing Steel Historical Developments

48x33mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Fracture Toughness - Hardness Relationship for Through Hardening HSS's

56x33mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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Transverse (L-C) vs. Longitudinal (C-L) Fracture Toughness of HSS's for Bearings
92x57mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Experimental vs. Modelled KIC values for three different HSS's

410x248mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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Fracture Toughness Information on Pyrowear 675 Core Steel
363x249mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Paris' Law Region (Region II) of Fatigue Crack Growth Curve

54x39mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Summary of Paris' Law (Stable Crack Growth) Data

210x126mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Bearing Steel Yield Strength versus K_{IC}

209x125mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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Bearing Steel Yield Strength versus Log Calculated Plastic Zone Size
60x36mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Transverse (L-C) vs. Longitudinal (C-L) Blunt U-Notch Impact Toughness Properties at room temperature for HSS's [ref. 8]

56x31mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Impact Toughness of PM Grades (ASP2055 and AMS 6560) vs. M50 at Room Temperature: U and V Notches
(Plotted Error bars are Standard Deviations)

62x40mm (300 x 300 DPI)

U-Notch Impact Toughness vs. Hardness (at RT) for Through Hardened HSS's
68x45mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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U-Notch Impact Toughness (Resiliency) in Transverse or Radial fracture as a Function of Temperature for Through Hardened HSS's

63x39mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Impact Toughness (un-notched sample) at room temperature for M50 NiL steel with different surface diffusion layers

497x262mm (300 x 300 DPI)